

Full Length Research Paper

Effect of plant spacing and rice variety on vegetative growth and rice performance at acidic conditions of Iyanomo, South-South Nigeria

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Received 5 October 2019; Accepted 12 November, 2019

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the major staple food crops for about 65% of the world's population as the crop is valued for its food contents. The recognition of poor performance of local rice varieties suggests that priority should be given to improved rice varieties with good performance including adaptability potential. Although cultivation of rice is a common practice in Nigeria, little is known about the response of rice crop to different spacing in Iyanomo. In Iyanomo village, planting rice has been hampered by lack of improved varieties. A rice field experiment was conducted at RRIN Headquarters, Iyanomo during the main wet cropping season in 2017. The objective of the study was to evaluate the influence of plant spacing on early performance (vegetative growth) of two rice varieties (NERICA 2 and NERICA 7) in local environments of Iyanomo using NERICA 1 (a high-yielding, disease-resistant and early-maturing upland rice variety as standard). The factorial experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design in a split-plot arrangement with five replications. The three NERICA varieties were planted at three spacing (10 x 10 cm; 20 x 20 cm; and 30 x 30 cm). Organic manure (cow dung fertilizer) and inorganic fertilizer (Urea) were applied prior to planting at the rate of 3,000 kg ha⁻¹ and 100 kg ha⁻¹ at 2 weeks after planting respectively. Weeds were adequately controlled using hand hoe. At 6 weeks after planting, plants were measured and the data on plant height, leaf length and leaf width were recorded from six randomly sampled plants within the middle of each sub-plot measuring 1.7 x 2.4 m (4.08 m²) excluding border plants. The operation was repeated at weekly interval (for a period of six weeks and at the end of the

experiment, the yields of the rice straw was determined, per hectare, from a plot measuring 1.7 x 2.4 m (4.08 m²) at 9 weeks after transplanting. The statistical software 'R STUDIO' was used to analyze the data (for plant height, leaf length and leaf width) and LSD at 5% probability level was used as the mean separation. Results indicate that in NERICA 1, the best spacing observed for the highest plant height and leaf length was 30 x 30 cm, while in NERICA 2, 20 x 20 cm had higher values for plant height, leaf length, and leaf width. For leaf width, the relatively high density at which the two rice varieties performed optimally was 20 x 20 cm suggesting that the spacing allowed maximum utilization of growth resources. The spacing of 10 x 10 cm had no effect on plant height, leaf length and leaf width for NERICA 1 and NERICA 2. The 30 x 30 cm spacing became more important in determining the leaf length and leaf width in NERICA 1 and NERICA 2. Similarly, 20 x 20 cm spacing had a larger and positive effect on the plant width of both varieties. The yields of rice straw indicated that the higher the plant populations, the higher the straw yields. NERICA 1 had the best straw yield. A spacing of 10 x 10 cm is recommended for straw production. The observed difference suggests that performance among the varieties was due to spacing. This paper provides an overview of progress in testing the vegetative growth of rice varieties. It is recommended that further work on the rice varieties be conducted on grain yields.

Keywords: Plant spacing, NERICA, swamp rice, upland rice, variety

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is an energy source for two-thirds of the world population, providing about 20% of energy

and 15% of the protein that human needs (Barberena *et al.*, 2011). It is the foremost staple food crop of great

social and economic importance for more than 50% of the world's population. While World production of rice is estimated at 450 million tonnes, the utilization figure is put at 510 million tonnes (FAO, 2018). Between 2007 and 2010, rice consumption in Africa increased at a rate of 4.4% per year, despite the upsurge in rice price during the food crisis (Africa Rice Center, 2012). With this, rice is the staple food for more than half of the world's population, contributing over 20% of the total calorie intake of humans (Seck *et al.*, 2012). The leading producers of this cereal worldwide are China, India, and Indonesia which together account for over 50 % of the world's total production (FAO, 2018).

Rice can be grown in a wide range of locations and climates. It can grow from altitude of sea level to 3000 meters above sea level (masl) with rainfall ranges from 800-2000 mm and its optimum temperature ranges from 25-35°C. There are primarily four ecosystems where rice is grown: irrigated, rainfed lowland, upland, and flood-prone. Each of these environments has its own ideal growing conditions, as well as limiting factors. Rainfed Upland Rice is grown in Asia, Africa, and Latin America. In sub-Saharan Africa, Nigeria is the leading producer of rice, with total production of 7.2 million tonnes (FAO, 2018). Rice yields are constrained by inadequate water control, low soil fertility, soil acidity and further hampered by biotic stresses such as blast, stem borers, termites and weeds. Gaps between attainable and actual yields are high, even in input-intensive systems. New rice for Africa (NERICA) are inter specific lines developed through hybridization of two cultivated rice, *Oryza sativa* (Asian rice) and *Oryza glaberrima* (Africa rice), with desirable traits. The NERICA varieties are modern rice suitable for the upland rice ecology of sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) and are superior regarding weed competitiveness, drought tolerance, and pest or disease resistance and have higher yielding potentials than traditional varieties. These qualities enable them present several advantages over traditional rice varieties including higher protein contents. NERICA varieties are planted on more than 700,000 ha across Africa showing positive impacts on rice productivity and farmers' livelihoods. These varieties, which are adapted to a wide range of agro-ecological conditions, include:

- (a) 18 NERICAs for upland (dryland) ecologies.
- (b) 60 lowland NERICAs for rain-fed and irrigated lowlands (wetland).

The use of NERICA varieties as planting materials for cultivation is aimed at using improved rice varieties for improved production.

Importance of plant spacing on growth and development of crops

One of the most important factors in improving vegetative growth together with yield components in crop production

is correct spacing. While planting any crop, it is important to space appropriately depending on the type of crop, size, and root systems. Those with wider roots and leaves need much bigger space than those with smaller roots. Different annual crops should be well spaced to achieve the best results and there are recommended guidelines. Overcrowding of crops may reduce yields and it may also lower quality of the fruits produced because of competition for light and soil nutrients. Similarly, if crops are planted too close to one another, it may be hard for the farmer to walk about in the farm during weeding, spraying pesticides, monitoring crop growth and harvesting. Planting too few plants in the field can also be a problem as plants like rice and maize that require a certain number of neighbouring plants to pollinate really need those neighbours and so planting too few plants may be undesirable. Proper plant spacing is important regarding nutrients uptake, disease management, weeding, ease of harvesting, and increased yields. Spacing determines plant population and the main aim of correct spacing is to obtain maximum number of plants per unit area for maximum utilization of the environment and growth resources. While wide spacing leads to few number of plants (and in some cases low yields), close spacing leads to overcrowding of plants and competition for nutrients and other resources. Therefore, correctly spaced crops, which produce yield of high quality, are acceptable in the cropping systems. Plant population affects vegetative growth and crop yields by imposing competition among plants for nutrients, moisture, sunlight and other growth resources. Establishment of an acceptable population of rice seedlings is paramount to obtaining high yields as in cotton crop (Christiansen and Rowland, 1981). The definition of an acceptable plant population, however, varies by location, environment, cultivar and grower preference (Silvertooth *et al.*, 1999). Rice is very responsive to high light intensity. Cognizant of these facts, this study was conducted to investigate the effect of plant spacing on vegetative growth and straw yield of rice in the humid environment of Iyanomo in the South-South region of Nigeria.

Working on adoption of new rice for Africa (NERICA) technologies in Ekiti State, Nigeria, Ojo *et al.*, (2018) reported that NERICA 7 with mean adoption score of 2.25 was one of the improved rice varieties suitable for cultivation in Southern Nigeria. Rice is cultivated virtually in the entire agro-ecological zones in Nigeria (Sulaiman *et al.*, 2014). But the main production ecologies for rice in Nigeria are rain-fed lowland, rain-fed upland, irrigated lowland, deep water floating and mangrove swamp. Of these, rain-fed lowland rice has the largest share of the rice (50%) and rice production. The average Nigerian consumes 24.8 Kg of rice per year representing 90% of total World's rice consumption and 90% calories intake (World Bank, 1999; IRRI, 2001; Bamidele1 *et al.*, 2010). Nigeria is currently the largest rice producing country in

Africa. This is as the result of conscientious efforts by the current administration to place more emphasis on agrarian production (Udemezue, 2018). With the available literature, annual rice production in Nigeria has increased from 5.5 million tons in 2015 to 5.8 million tons in 2017. The consumption rate now is 7.9 million tones and the production rate has increased to 5.8 tons per annum. The increase was as a result of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)'s Anchor Borrowers Program with a total of 12 million rice producers and four million hectares of FADAMA rice land (RIFAN, 2017). Despite the importance of rice, the area cultivated to rice still appears small in the year 2000. For instance, of the 25 million hectares of land cultivated for various food crops, only about 6.4% was cultivated to rice in the year 2000 (Akanke, 2000). According to Nwilene *et al.* (2016), the potential land area for rice cultivation in Nigeria ranges from 4.6 to 4.9 million hectares. Of these, only about 1.7 million ha or 35% of the available land area is presently cropped to rice (Imolehin and Wada, 2005). The unavailability of appropriate technologies has been identified as one of the factors limiting production of lowland rice in Nigeria. New high-yielding, early-maturing (< 90 – 100 days) lowland varieties of NERICA are undergoing agronomic evaluation in Nigeria and several other countries (Nwilene *et al.*, 2016). Togola *et al.* (2012) reported that NERICA 1, NERICA 2 and NERICA 7 are among the best rice varieties tolerant to termite infestation. Currently, the performance of NERICA 1 and NERICA 2 at Iyanomo is not known. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to access the performance of two varieties of New Rice for Africa together with a standard check variety grown at Iyanomo in South-South Nigeria and select the ideal spacing for optimum growth of the three varieties for small-scale farmers (with farm holdings of less than 1 ha) who cultivate most of the rice produced in Nigeria.

Objectives

- (i) To determine the influence of varied spacing on the early growth performance of upland NERICA rice varieties.
- (ii) To determine the vegetative growth of NERICA varieties in Iyanomo environment.
- (iii) To select and test NERICA rice varieties for adaptability to the Iyanomo environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Site description

The experiment was conducted during the rainy season of 2017, in a rain-fed environment at Iyanomo, South-South region of Nigeria. Iyanomo is located at about 19

km from Benin City, along the Benin–Sapele Express/Highway. The area lies between longitude 5°35' and 5°55'E and latitude 6°05' and 6°25'N. The land is part of the Coastal Plain Sands of the Niger Delta Basin. The soils are derived from unconsolidated sedimentary deposits of the Miocene-Pleistocene period. They were described as the Coastal Plain Sands that is partly marine, estuarine and deltaic or fluviolacustrine in origin. The climate of the area is humid tropical, characterized by deep, porous sandy to loamy sand surface soils overlying sandy loam to sandy clay sub soil. Soil reaction is usually strongly acid to very strongly acid. The soils have very low base status and low cation exchange capacities (CEC), mainly described as Paleudalfs, Paleudults and Dystropepts. Dominant rainy and a less influencing dry season alternate annually. The rainfall is bimodal with a higher peak in July and a lower peak in September. Pre-experimental values of the soil's physico-chemical properties indicate that it was strongly acidic (pH 5.5), poor in organic matter (12.5 g kg⁻¹ soil) and total nitrogen (0.9 g kg⁻¹ soil) and high in available P (29.0 mg kg⁻¹ soil).

Experimental materials and design

Good quality seeds without insect damage and no contaminations (weed seeds, stones etc) with high percentage of viability (> 80%) from two accessions of rice (NERICA 2 and NERICA 7 and a standard check variety (NERICA 1) germplasm were collected from the National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRAB) gene bank in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The three accessions of rice were put in two different pieces of white cloth and were separately dipped in hot water for about two seconds in order to break their seed dormancy. After breaking of seed dormancy, the rice seeds were sown in trays containing top soil on 9th May 2017. The rice seeds were planted in a depth of about 1.5 cm in the top soil, and covered with dry grasses to create a humid environment that quickened the germination of the rice seeds, and the seeds were watered daily in the trays. Sprouting of the rice seeds commenced after four days of planting in the trays. After sprouting, the seedlings were allowed to stay in the trays for a period of five weeks prior to transferring to the field. Specifically, on 13th June 2017 (35 DAS), seedlings of the three rice accessions were manually transplanted to experimental plots duly allocated to National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRAB) at RRIN Headquarters, Iyanomo in Edo State, Nigeria. Depending on the spacing adopted, seedlings were transplanted into the stand (hill) in all the treatments. Factorial combination of three plant spacing (10 x 10, 20 x 20, 30 x 30 cm) and two rice varieties (NERICA 2 and NERICA 7 and a standard check variety (NERICA 1) treatments were laid out in

randomized complete block design in split-plot arrangements with five replicates. Gross plot size of 9.5 x 7.3 m was used for the treatments, which were arranged within each variety with three different spacing as the main plots and three varieties as the sub-plots. Each accession was divided into five blocks and labeled as block A, B, C, D, E and planted with different plant densities (1,000,000, 250,000, and 111,111 plants ha⁻¹) for the 10 x 10, 20 x 20, 30 x 30 cm spacing respectively.

Scope and purpose of the study

This study analyzed the effects of spacing on the vegetative growth of rice varieties in Iyanomo, South-South Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the plant heights, leaf length, leaf width and straw yield of rice varieties and determined the spacing that influence vegetative growth and straw yields of the rice varieties in Iyanomo, Ikpoba Okha local government area of Edo State, Nigeria.

Crop management and treatments

On 13th June 2017, cow-dung fertilizer (organic fertilizer), whose composition is environmentally friendly and costs less than other sources of fertilizers, was broadcast in the field at 3,000 kg ha⁻¹ prior to transplanting the rice into the field. On June 27, 2017 (fourteen days after transplanting), urea fertilizer (a straight or single fertilizer) was applied to the soil by line application at 100 kg ha⁻¹ to enhance the nutrients composition of the soil. Five weeks after transplanting into the field (July 21, 2017), weeds, which are the major constraints to rice production in Nigeria, were adequately controlled using best agronomic practices as weeding operation was carried out manually using hand hoe. The weeding operation was repeated at six weeks interval.

Data collection/measurements

Six weeks after transplanting to the field, and as the scope of the trial was limited to vegetative growth only, plant height, leaf length and leaf width of the individual plants were measured and the data were recorded from six randomly sampled plants within the middle of each sub-plot measuring 1.7 x 2.4 m (4.08 m²) excluding border plants. The operation was repeated at weekly interval for a period of six weeks and at the end of the experiment, the yields of the rice straw was determined, per hectare, from the sub plots each measuring 1.7 x 2.4 m (4.08 m²).

Data analysis

Data on the plant samples of selected variables were taken on 25/07/2017, 01/08/2017, 08/08/2017,

15/08/2017 and 22/08/2017 (i.e. 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 weeks after transplanting into the field) and the statistical software 'RSTUDIO' was used to analyze the data (for plant height, leaf width, leaf length) at 5% probability level. Straw yields were determined at 9 weeks after transplanting.

RESULTS

Physicochemical properties of soil

The soil physico-chemical properties at Iyanomo are presented in (Table 1). As it can be seen from the (Table 1), the soil was sandy loam and acidic with pH of 5.7, clay 100 g kg⁻¹, silt 19.6 g kg⁻¹ and sand 880.4 g kg⁻¹. Organic Carbon, which is important in determining organic matter, was 13.8 g kg⁻¹. Organic matter, which is important in building surface soil fertility, was 23.8. Total Nitrogen was 3.3 g kg⁻¹; available phosphorus in the soil was 8.03 mg kg⁻¹ while effective cation exchange capacity (CEC) was 4.88 cmol kg⁻¹.

Vegetative and morphophysiological growth of the rice plant

Differences were observed depending on the spacing used for the three rice varieties (Plate 1). Within each spacing (population), plant height was always significantly ($P < 0.05$) taller in NERICA 7 (Table 2). Leaf length and leaf width were shorter in NERICA 1 (the standard check as control) compared with NERICA 7 (Table 2) in all spacing. Leaf width within 20 x 20 cm spacing increased from 1.1 cm (NERICA 1) to 1.7 cm (NERICA 2) (Table 2). Plant height in the study was significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected by spacing (population). Although differences in plant height between the populations were apparent by 6 weeks after transplanting, significant differences did not appear until 8 weeks after transplanting. The data obtained show that 20 x 20 cm spacing had a significant advantage over the other two spacing for most of the growth variables of the varieties (Table 3) that were measured (Plant Height and Leaf Width) in NERICA 2. Thus, NERICA 2 rice variety planted at 20 x 20 cm spacing had the highest growth regarding plant height, which with 110 cm significantly ($p < 0.001$) outweighed the other spacing by 12% (Table 3). Spacing of 30 x 30 cm generated the second most significant plant height, with 96 cm in NERICA 2 that was higher than rice planted on the 10 x 10 cm spacing (80 cm). Table 3 also show a strong correlation of 94.4 % between spacing and variety ($P < 0.05$). The growth estimated in terms of leaf width in 30 x 30 cm spacing repeated this trend with some variations (Table 2). This is in conformity with earlier observations of Bishnu *et al.* (2013) who reported that lower seeding density resulted

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of Iyanomo Soils.

Soil Properties	Characteristics
Sand (g kg ⁻¹)	880.4
Silt (g kg ⁻¹)	19.6
Clay (g kg ⁻¹)	100.0
Texture (g kg ⁻¹)	LS
pH (H ₂ O)	5.7
Organic Carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	13.8
Total Nitrogen (g kg ⁻¹)	3.3
Available Phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹)	8.03
Exchangeable Calcium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.15
Exchangeable Magnesium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.85
Exchangeable Sodium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.1
Exchangeable Potassium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.18
Exchangeable Acidity (cmol kg ⁻¹)	2.6
ECEC* (cmol kg ⁻¹)	4.88
Base sat. (%)	46.72
Manganese (mg kg ⁻¹)	121.08
Iron (mg kg ⁻¹)	70.25
Copper (mg kg ⁻¹)	6.96
Zinc (mg kg ⁻¹)	17.32

*ECEC = Effective Cation Exchange Capacity.
Data Source: Waizah *et al.*, 2012

Table 2. Effects of plant spacing on vegetative growth of NERICA rice varieties at Iyanomo.

Dependent Variable: Observation					
Variety	Spacing	Plant status	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
1.00	1.00	1.00	0.9480	0.13554	5
		2.00	68.6960	5.79708	5
		3.00	44.4540	2.88841	5
		Total	38.0327	29.21790	15
	2.00	1.00	1.0880	.21464	5
		2.00	75.5240	11.80210	5
		3.00	49.7920	5.68056	5
		Total	42.1347	32.70864	15
	3.00	1.00	1.0120	.22488	5
		2.00	74.1320	13.52240	5
		3.00	48.5940	7.11939	5
		Total	41.2460	32.40993	15
	Total	1.00	1.0160	.19071	15
		2.00	72.7840	10.53289	15
		3.00	47.6133	5.62925	15
		Total	40.4711	30.81283	45
2.00	1.00	1.00	1.2100	.25288	5
		2.00	76.6040	14.26930	5
		3.00	47.1220	4.79769	5
		Total	41.6453	33.10413	15
	2.00	1.00	1.7000	.27102	5
		2.00	95.8900	12.75539	5
		3.00	57.7560	3.55885	5
		Total	51.7820	40.66309	15
	3.00	1.00	1.6620	.28367	5
		2.00	92.6080	12.22151	5
		3.00	59.5120	3.89753	5
		Total	51.2607	39.50327	15
	Total	1.00	1.5240	.33960	15
		2.00	88.3673	14.94624	15
		3.00	54.7967	6.82934	15
		Total	48.2293	37.33013	45

7.00	1.00	1.00	1.1100	.18655	5
		2.00	84.5120	10.83494	5
		3.00	57.4940	10.01020	5
		Total	47.7053	36.81897	15
	2.00	1.00	1.3640	.14153	5
		2.00	110.2040	17.23374	5
		3.00	60.1660	8.66840	5
		Total	57.2447	47.18355	15
	3.00	1.00	1.1040	.17416	5
		2.00	89.8260	12.80517	5
		3.00	56.5080	5.04520	5
		Total	49.1460	38.58507	15
	Total	1.00	1.1927	.20016	15
		2.00	94.8473	17.22287	15
		3.00	58.0560	7.74144	15
		Total	51.3653	40.39114	45
Total	1.00	1.00	1.0893	.21436	15
		2.00	76.6040	12.08253	15
		3.00	49.6900	8.45502	15
		Total	42.4611	32.67942	45
	2.00	1.00	1.3840	.32706	15
		2.00	93.8727	19.69997	15
		3.00	55.9047	7.44051	15
		Total	50.3871	40.18450	45
	3.00	1.00	1.2593	.36671	15
		2.00	85.5220	14.58255	15
		3.00	54.8713	6.98682	15
		Total	47.2176	36.37930	45
	Total	1.00	1.2442	.32613	45
		2.00	85.3329	16.98364	45
		3.00	53.4887	7.96581	45
		Total	46.6886	36.41641	135

- (a) Variety: N1=1, N2= 2, N7=7
 (b) Spacing: 10 x10 = 1, 20x20= 2, 30x30=3
 (c) Plant status: Leaf width = 1, Plant height = 2, Leaf length = 3
 (d) R Squared = 0.950 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.944)

in the formation of more productive tillers, superior performance for all morpho-physiological and yield components, resulting in higher grain yields over higher seeding density.

Faisal-ur-Rasoolm *et al.*, (2013) indicated that closer spacing of 15 cm x 10 cm, 15 cm x 15 cm and 15 cm x 20 cm were superior to wider spacing of 30 cm x 10 cm, 20 cm x 20 cm and 15 cm x 25 cm by producing more effective rice tillers per unit area, higher plant height, higher leaf area index and total dry matter accumulation. However, Bishnu *et al.* (2013) on the other hand reported that wider spacing (25 cm x 25 cm, and 30 cm x 30 cm) produced significantly higher rice tillers, panicles per m², longer and weighty panicles, and higher grain yield than closer spacing (15 cm x 15 cm). While Ogbodo *et al.* (2010) observed that plant height and number of rice tillers were significantly higher when crops were transplanted at 30 cm x 30 cm than at 10 cm x 10 cm and 20 cm x 20 cm. Nwokwu, (2015) on the contrary, reported that plant spacing at 40 cm x 40 cm only

produced higher number of tillers, number of leaves, shorter days to 50% heading and increase in 1000 grain weight whereas plant spacing at 30 cm x 30 cm recorded longest panicles, more number of panicles and paddy yield but with no significant differences in plant height for the two different spacing. The authors attributed the observation to the presence of adequate plant nutrients in the soil for normal growth.

According to Ogbodo *et al.* (2010), rice transplanted at 30 cm x 30 cm spacing yielded 2.36 and 1.32 t ha⁻¹ significantly higher grains than those transplanted at 10 cm x 10 cm and 20 cm x 20 cm respectively. NERICA 2 and NERICA 7 adapted to the 10 x 10 cm spacing than NERICA 1 as NERICA 1 appeared particularly poorly adapted to the 10 x 10 cm spacing. NERICA 2 tended to give consistently longer leaf length in all the spacing, indicating wide adaptability of NERICA 2 to all the spacing. Regarding leaf width, this variable showed high growth in the 20 x 20 cm (Table 2) for all varieties. For plant height and leaf length, the spacing selected for

Table 3. Tests of between-subjects effects.

Dependent Variable: Observation					
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	168843.485 ^a	14	12060.249	163.320	0.000
Intercept	294276.332	1	294276.332	3985.093	0.000
Variety * Spacing	1910.414	6	318.402	4.312	0.001
Variety * Plant status	164102.442	6	27350.407	370.379	0.000
Error	8861.315	120	73.844		
Total	471981.132	135			
Corrected Total	177704.800	134			

Table 4. Weather data during the cropping season (January to October 2017) at Iyanomo.

Month	Important Climatic Parameters					Rainfall (mm)	Wind Speed
	Temperature (°C)			Relative Humidity (%)			
	Max Temp	Min Tem	Ave Temp	Max RH	Min RH		
Jan	24.9	23.5	24.2	33.7	22.6	26.0	1.3
Feb	26.6	24.9	25.8	36.9	26.2	26.0	2.1
Mar	27.4	26.3	26.9	36.0	24.7	53.8	2.8
Apr	28.5	25.7	27.1	33.8	23.3	91.3	3.9
May	27.2	25.3	26.2	32.7	24.1	66.2	2.4
Jun	33.6	22.6	28.1	33.5	22.8	315	3.4
Jul	31.5	22.4	27.0	31.7	29.7	402.2	2.5
Aug	24.4	24.4	24.4	31.7	23.6	598.6	2.1
Sep	26.1	22.7	24.8	32.3	23.2	150.8	2.5
Oct	25.8	25.5	25.7	33.3	22.9	103	2.1
Total						1,832.9	

NERICA 1 and NERICA 2 varieties was 30 x 30 cm and 20 x 20 cm respectively. NERICA 7 performed outstandingly as it had a mean plant height of 90 cm, leaf length of 61 cm and leaf width of 1.18 cm. Regarding plant height in the difference spacing, NERICA 7 had 70.2 cm in the 30 x 30 cm spacing, 58.0 in the 20 x 20 cm and 53.3 cm in the 10 x 10 cm spacing. For leaf width, NERICA 7 had a mean of 1.18 cm in the 20 x 20 cm spacing. The 20 x 20 cm spacing had the longest leaf width and was followed by 1.17 in the 30 x 30 cm spacing. For NERICA 7, the ideal spacing for maximum growth in plant height and leaf length is 20 x 20 cm and 30 x 30 cm respectively. For straw yields, results indicate that NERICA 1 performed better than the other two varieties. In particular, the 10 x 10 plant spacing of NERICA 1 had 2,720 Kg ha⁻¹. This was followed by the 20 x 20 cm spacing with 1,572 kg ha⁻¹ (Figure 1). The combined results showed the following performance and influence of spacing on: plant height, 20 x 20 cm > 30 x 30 cm > 10 x 10 cm; leaf length, 30 x 30 cm > 20 x 20 cm > 10 x 10 cm; and leaf width, 20 x 20 cm > 30 x 30 cm > 10 x 10 cm. The combined results concerning the vegetative parameters confirm the selection of optimum spacing for each of the rice varieties.

DISCUSSION

For all rice varieties, 30 x 30 cm spacing had its greatest effect on the vegetative development compared with 10 x 10 cm spacing. Testing rice varieties at different spacing, other researchers have found leaf length of rice to be primarily determined by the density of rice (Baloc *et al.*, 2002; Bishnu *et al.*, 2013; Nwokwu, 2015; Moro *et al.*, 2016). Within the scope of this study, the use of NERICA varieties as planting materials, at Iyanomo environment, was aimed at using improved varieties for improved performance using vegetative growth as starter. In NERICA 1, the best spacing observed for the highest plant height and leaf length was 30 x 30 cm. In NERICA 2, 20 x 20 cm had highest values for plant height but not for leaf length, while in NERICA 7, the best spacing for plant height was recorded in the 30 x 30 cm (70 cm). The 20 x 20 cm and 10 x 10 cm spacing had 58 cm and 53 cm respectively. The relatively high density at which all the rice varieties performed optimally was 20 x 20 cm suggesting that the spacing allowed maximum utilization of growth resources. Optimal population density has been known (De Datta 1986; De Datta *et al.*, 1988) to effectively utilize available resources and recovery of

Figure 1. Effects of plant spacing on rice straw production of three NERICA varieties at Iyanomo, Edo State, Nigeria.

Plate 1. NERICA Rice varieties growing at Iyanomo environment, South-South Nigeria, West Africa.

applied nitrogen. The spacing of 30 x 30 cm has no effect on plant height and leaf width for NERICA 2. However, the 30 x 30 cm spacing became more important in determining the leaf length in NERICA 1 and NERICA 7. In contrast to the 30 x 30 cm spacing, 20 x 20 cm spacing had largest effect on the plant width of all varieties. Planting at 10 x 10 cm spacing had a positive effect on the plant height, but had no effect on leaf length. It appears, most likely, that genotypic differences were also responsible for the observed difference in the leaf width. However, the observed difference suggests that performance among the three varieties was mainly due to spacing and partly genotypes. Recently, 20 x 20 cm spacing was described as the best for maximum yield of rice, following findings from studies (Nwoku, 2015; Moro *et al.*, 2016). According to Moro *et al.* (2016), spacing of 20 cm x 20 cm, which corresponds to 20 stands per m², produced significantly higher grain yields and therefore was recommended for the rain-fed lowlands (inland valleys and flood plains) of three rice varieties in Ghana. Similarly, Baloch *et al.* (2002) reported that plant density at spacing of 20 x 20 cm² was more effective and gave significantly higher grain yield per plot than the 25 x 25 cm spacing and was therefore, most suitable for obtaining maximum yields. Two major weaver birds were found in the rice field, the village weaver bird (*Ploceus cucullatus*), and the red-headed quelea (*Quelea erythrops*). Although, the frequent presence of weaver birds in the rice field was not a surprise, it was viewed as a concern and cause for action. Nevertheless, the field team took avoiding action and used wire gauge and fenced round the field and this avoided damage to the rice seeds. The results of this current study reinforce the need for the assessment of bird's damage on rice yields at Iyanomo as part of future studies. The intense work of rice breeders and experts at Africa Rice Center had been remarkably original and fruitful and resulted to the development of NERICA varieties.

Conclusion

The study indicates that a significant vegetative growth can be obtained in NERICA 1, NERICA 2, and NERICA 7 rice varieties with 20 x 20 and 30 x 30 cm spacing. The results of the study shown that the use of 20 x 20 cm spacing can produce vegetative growth of NERICA 2 and NERICA 7. For leaf width of NERICA 1, the results showed only a moderate growth response to spacing. Spacing stimulated plant height in the early growth phase of NERICA 2 and NERICA 7, enhanced the leaf length of both varieties, and increased the leaf width of both varieties. Additionally, the results indicate that the difference in vegetative growth among NERICA 1, NERICA 2, and NERICA 7 is due to Spacing. These results reveal that potential of growing the rice varieties in

Iyanomo exists for NERICA 2 and NERICA 7 compared to NERICA 1 (the control or standard check). This indicates that NERICA 2 and NERICA 7 with good performance should be exploited in Iyanomo and areas in the Niger Delta region with similar weather conditions as they are more useful for folder production. Planting at 20 x 20 cm spacing increased plant height in NERICA 1, NERICA 2, and NERICA 7. This positive effect was due primarily to the ideal spacing. For leaf length, 30 x 30 cm spacing is recommended for NERICA 1 and NERICA 2, while 20 x 20 cm spacing is recommended for NERICA 7. Using NERICA 2 and NERICA 7 in the lowland area of Iyanomo is a high priority. For vegetative growth, we conclude therefore that NERICA 2 and NERICA 7 should be exploited in Iyanomo environment (Table 4.) using spacing of 20 x 20 cm for plant height and leaf width and 30 x 30 cm for leaf length. The yields of rice straw indicated that the higher the plant populations, the higher the straw yields. NERICA 1 had the best straw yield. A spacing of 10 x 10 cm is recommended for straw production. These conclusions pertained to vegetative growth of the rice varieties. It should be noted, however, that other factors such as grain yields, 1000 grain weight, number of tillers, number of panicles, panicle weight etc should be considered when determining performance of rice in Iyanomo environment. It is expedient for more rice trials to be conducted at Iyanomo environment. It is, therefore, recommended that further work on the rice varieties be conducted and mainly focused on grain yield factors. This will ensure that the main economic part of rice is conscientiously considered. Information from this preliminary study (vegetative growth) carried out at Iyanomo may apply to rice cultivation in West and Central Africa as results from the current study indicate that these varieties can be grown easily in the humid lowland of West and Central Africa.

Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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